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The Impact Of Street Hawking On The Education Of Young Girls In Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of street hawking on the educational outcomes of young girls in Katsina State, Nigeria, focusing on school attendance, academic performance, and the socioeconomic factors influencing their participation in street hawking. Data were collected from a sample of 150 respondents, with key demographic indicators including age, school level, and household income levels, which provide context for understanding the economic pressures faced by these young girls. Utilizing an independent samples t-test, the study compares the academic performance between girls involved in street hawking and those who are not, revealing a statistically significant difference in mean performance scores. Findings indicate that street hawking detrimentally impacts academic achievement, with students involved in hawking scoring lower on average than their non-hawking counterparts. This suggests that the demands of street hawking driven largely by economic necessity consume time and energy, thereby hindering the girls' educational engagement and performance. The results underscore the broader implications of child labor on female education in low-income communities, pointing to a need for targeted interventions that address the economic and cultural factors compelling girls into street hawking. Recommendations include implementing social welfare programs, enforcing stricter child labor laws, and providing school-based support initiatives to mitigate the adverse educational impacts on young girls involved in street hawking.

Keywords: Street Hawking, Education, Young Girls.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Street hawking is the practice of selling goods and services in public spaces, is a widespread phenomenon in many developing countries, including Nigeria. In Katsina State, this informal economic activity is particularly prevalent among young girls, who often take to the streets to support their families financially. While street hawking can provide immediate economic benefits, it poses significant challenges, especially for the education and development of young girls. In their study, Senna (2022) delved into the prevalent practice of street hawking in developing nations, specifically focusing on the direct retail sale of goods in bustling urban areas. This phenomenon is widespread, particularly in numerous African cities, towns, and district capitals. Senna's research aimed to examine the impact of street hawking on the educational opportunities of young female hawkers residing in Ghana's Volta region. Street hawking, defined as the practice of directly vending retail products on bustling urban streets, presents a pervasive challenge in developing nations, with notable impacts in African cities, towns, and district capitals. The emergence of street hawking is often attributed to factors such as rural-urban migration, unemployment, poverty, and a growing number of

school dropouts. For many individuals, street hawking serves as a means to generate income and supplement household finances. Youth migrating from impoverished rural areas to urban centers in pursuit of non-existent employment opportunities often find themselves resorting to street hawking due to a lack of education and employable skills (Asiedu et al., 2008). Across various regions globally, numerous individuals heavily rely, either entirely or partially, on street sales as their livelihood (Akuoko, 2013). Small-scale trading, particularly on the streets, is a vital component of Africa's informal economy, frequently employed by those with limited education, notably women (Akuoko, 2013). Urban streets are teeming with vendors selling a diverse range of goods, including vegetables, furniture, clothing, and technology (Skinner, 2008). Street vending offers a viable source of employment for urban residents with modest education and financial resources, facilitating accessibility for disadvantaged populations (Mitullah, 2003). The growth of street vending in Africa is significantly influenced by urbanization and migration, as individuals from rural areas flock to cities in pursuit of non-existent job opportunities. This phenomenon is observable in major urban centers such as Accra, Kumasi, Sekondi-Takoradi, and Tamale, where street hawkers often congregate near convenient market areas and churches, particularly on Sundays, to attract buyers (Akuoko, 2013).

This research aims to investigate the impact of street hawking on the education of young girls in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study seeks to understand how the demands of street hawking interfere with school attendance, academic performance, and overall educational outcomes. Furthermore, it explores the socioeconomic factors that compel young girls to engage in street hawking and examines the associated health and safety risks.

1.1 The Socio-Economic Impact and Challenges of Street Hawking

The phenomenon of street hawking is a critical human development issue that affects many societies worldwide, particularly in Third World countries. In nations like Pakistan, a primary driver of this issue is the lack of access to basic education and the high dropout rate among school-aged children, often due to poverty. Additionally, the structural adjustment program implemented in Pakistan aims to alleviate poverty and enhance access to infrastructural facilities, including educational services for the less privileged (Tufail, 2005). The issue of street children has gained global attention because of its far-reaching implications for their survival and future prospects. What was once a rare occurrence, the presence of street children in major cities across the globe has now become a pressing global concern. In today's fast-paced world, many people are unable to visit traditional marketplaces for shopping, making street hawking a convenient and affordable alternative. Street hawkers offer goods at relatively lower prices, although the quality of these products may sometimes be compromised. Supporting street hawkers is also cost-effective, as they sell items individually rather than in bulk, making them more accessible to a wider range of consumers. Moreover, street hawkers operate without restrictions on working hours, allowing for greater accessibility to their services (Davis, 2008). This issue is particularly pronounced in African cities, such as Accra, the capital of Ghana. In these regions, street hawking is largely driven by rural-to-urban migration, unemployment, and a growing number of school dropouts. For many, it provides a source of income and helps to supplement their family's finances. However, street hawking also exposes individuals to a range of risks, including accidents, loss of life, abuse, reproductive health issues, vulnerability to crime and prostitution, and other social problems (Davis, 2008). Additionally, street hawking hampers national economic progress because hawkers are often untaxed, resulting in a loss of potential government revenue. They also contribute to traffic congestion, leading to increased travel time, fuel expenses, and higher transportation costs, which further raise the overall cost of doing business. Hawkers typically operate in unsafe public locations, forcing them to navigate between moving vehicles in order to earn a living. This exposes them to numerous hazards, including inclement weather, crime, and other adverse conditions (International Labour Office, 2002). In many cases, street hawkers' aspirations remain unfulfilled, and they are trapped in this line of work merely to survive. Their job often involves running after moving vehicles to make sales. Unfortunately, the earnings of most street traders are meager and insufficient to cover basic needs such as shelter, food, and healthcare.

1.2 The Role of Women's Education in National Development

The significance of women's education extends beyond academic achievement; it plays a vital role in shaping their social behavior and overall societal contribution. Educated women are often regarded as

cultured, refined, and gentle in demeanor. Supporting this perspective, Egbuna (2007) describes an educated woman as one who exhibits qualities of politeness, respect, and gentleness, characteristics that make her well-suited to nurturing well-behaved children and contributing positively to the workforce. This influence extends to national development, as women's education equips them to assume leadership positions and drive societal progress. Tenebe (2011) further underscores the importance of women's education in fostering both individual and national growth. He emphasizes that educated women are better positioned to foster intellectual development within their families by sharing knowledge and values with their sons and husbands. This exchange of ideas and insights contributes to creating a more informed and progressive society. Tenebe also stresses that prioritizing women's education is essential not only for academic advancement but also for enhancing leadership opportunities, thereby strengthening national development efforts. Despite the recognized positive impact of educating women, significant challenges remain. Ogunyomi (2022) highlights that girl child education is crucial for national progress, as girls grow into future wives, mothers, workers, and leaders who shape the nation's future. However, barriers such as child marriage, child labor, inadequate policy implementation, and widespread poverty hinder girls' access to education, especially in underdeveloped and developing countries like Nigeria. Overcoming these challenges is imperative to ensure that women's education can fully contribute to the holistic development of the nation.

1.3 The Socio-Economic Impact of Street Hawking: Challenges and Educational Implications

Numerous studies have been conducted on the issue of street hawking, with the majority focusing on the challenges hawkers face, such as traffic accidents, reproductive health risks, and conflicts with law enforcement. Research has also explored the relationship between hawking and poverty, as well as other aspects of the street hawking phenomenon. Duh (2004) examined the societal effects of hawkers, particularly the traffic issues they contribute to. He shared personal experiences and highlighted the dangers hawkers encounter, including life-threatening situations. While extensive research exists on street hawking in countries like Ghana, there is limited literature on how street hawking affects the academic performance of young girls. This gap in research points to the need for further studies to better understand the problem and find solutions. Street hawking is a significant human development challenge, particularly in Third World countries. In Pakistan, for instance, a primary cause of street hawking is the lack of access to basic education, with many children dropping out of school due to poverty. The country's structural adjustment program, aimed at reducing poverty and improving access to essential services like education, has yet to fully address these issues (Tufail, 2005; Ali et al., 2004). The problem of street children has gained global attention due to its serious implications for their survival and future. In today's fast-paced world, where not everyone can visit traditional marketplaces, street hawking offers a quick and affordable alternative. Goods are sold at relatively lower prices, though their quality may be uncertain. Supporting street hawkers is easy and economical, as products are sold individually rather than in bulk, making them affordable. Additionally, street hawkers operate with flexible hours, allowing for greater accessibility (Davis, 2008). This practice, while convenient for consumers, poses significant challenges for the hawkers themselves, particularly in terms of health, safety, and education. Understanding these broader impacts is crucial for addressing the issue comprehensively.

1.4 The Detrimental Effects of Street Hawking on Child Rights and Education

Hawking, as defined by Olukosi et al. (2005), is a marketing strategy where multiple buyers and sellers exchange small amounts of goods simultaneously. The researcher expresses concern about this practice, particularly because many school-aged children are involved. According to Nseabasi and Oluwabamide (2010), street hawking violates the international convention on the rights of the child. Involving children in money-making activities is considered unethical, as it deprives them of their fundamental right to education. Fawole et al. (2003) highlighted that a significant portion of child hawkers are young girls who attend school during the day and hawk after school or on weekends, typically for their parents or guardians. In Nigeria, the number of children engaged in trade or labor, particularly in rural areas, has been rising, which negatively impacts their ability to pursue an education. Dustmann (2003) attributed this trend to several factors, including the cost of schooling, family dynamics, household and community characteristics, and the location and distance of formal

education centers. Cultural practices, such as polygamy and the desire for large families, further exacerbate poverty and illiteracy. Esweren (2001) emphasized that child street hawking endangers the survival of society by distorting government plans for juvenile education. It also hampers the acquisition of proper vocational skills and education, which in turn negatively affects the economic sector. Danesty and Okediran (2002) noted that street hawking among young students contributes to additional psychological issues, such as engagement in risky sexual behaviors and juvenile delinquency. These activities consume much of the students' school time, leading to poor academic performance and, in some cases, dropout syndrome.

Maryam (2023) investigate The Effect of Street Hawking on Girl Child Education In Katsina Local Government Area Katsina State, the study examines the multifaceted impact of street hawking on girl child education, including limited access to formal education, increased dropout rates, vulnerability to exploitation, reinforcement of gender stereotypes, and long-term economic implications. The present research seeks to address the critical gap in understanding the full impact of street hawking on the education of young girls in entire Katsina State considering the three geo political zones. It aims to explore how the demands of street hawking interfere with school attendance, academic performance, and educational outcomes. Furthermore, it examines the socioeconomic factors that drive young girls into street hawking and assesses the health and safety risks they face.

1.5 Research Questions

The following question was raised before commencing the research

- i. What are the impact of street hawking on school attendance?
- ii. What are the academic performance of young girls engaged in street hawking?
- iii. What are the socioeconomic factors driving young girls into street hawking?
- iv. What is the health and safety risks associated with street hawking for young girls?

1.6 Objectives of the Study

The aim of this research is to investigate and understand the impact of street hawking on the education of young girls in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study seeks to uncover the extent to which street hawking affects school attendance, academic performance, and overall educational outcomes, and to identify the underlying socioeconomic factors driving young girls into street hawking.

The objectives are:

- i. To investigate the impact of street hawking on school attendance
- ii. To evaluate the academic performance of young girls engaged in street hawking
- iii. To explore the socioeconomic factors driving young girls into street hawking
- iv. To examine the health and safety risks associated with street hawking for young girls
- v. To recommend strategies and interventions for mitigating the negative impact of street hawking on girls' education

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in the Katsina Local Government Area, located in Katsina State, northern Nigeria. Katsina serves as the capital of the state (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2007) and is situated approximately 160 miles east of Sokoto and 84 miles northwest of Kano, near the Niger border. The area is an agricultural hub, known for producing crops such as groundnuts, cotton, millet, and guinea corn, as well as for its peanut oil and steel mills. The majority of the population is Muslim, predominantly from the Fulani and Hausa ethnic groups.

2.2 Data collection

Young girls involved in street hawking, their parents/guardians, and educational authorities, ideally through schools, community centers and local organizations that work with street hawkers sample from selected communities and schools in Katsina State are the respondent of the provided questionnaire

2.3 Statistical Analysis

We used the Statistical package for social sciences SPSS Version 23 for the analysis the following test was made for the obtain data

T-tests: Compare academic performance between girls involved in street hawking and those who are not. Collect academic records or self-reported grades for comparison.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section presents a detailed analysis of the data collected to examine the impact of street hawking on the education of young girls in Katsina State, Nigeria. This chapter begins by describing the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including age, current school level, and household income, which provide context for understanding the socio-economic background of the participants. By exploring these variables, we can better appreciate the economic pressures that might drive these young girls to engage in street hawking. Furthermore, this chapter uses inferential statistical methods, specifically an independent samples t-test, to compare the academic performance of students involved in street hawking with those not involved. Through this analysis, we identify significant differences in academic outcomes between the two groups, highlighting the potential educational disadvantages faced by those engaged in hawking. The findings from this analysis provide insights into how street hawking activities, motivated primarily by economic need, may hinder the academic achievement of young girls. By interpreting these results, this chapter builds on existing research concerning child labor and education, and offers an evidence-based discussion on the implications of street hawking for educational attainment in low-income communities.

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents				
Age of the respondents	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
16-18	134	89.3	89.3	89.3
19-21	16	10.7	10.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0		
Current School Level				
Senior Secondary School	142	94.7	94.7%	94.7
Out of School	8	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0		
Household Income Level				
Below N10,000	49	32.7	32.7	32.7
N10,000-N30,000	44	29.3	29.3	62.0
N31,000-N50,000	8	5.3	5.3	67.3
Above N50,000	49	32.7	32.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0		
Are you currently involved in street hawking?				
Yes	78	52.0	52.0	52.0
No	72	48.0	48.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0		

The participants were predominantly within the age group of 16-18 years, representing 89.3% (n=134) of the total sample. Only 10.7% (n=16) of participants were between 19 and 21 years. This age distribution is consistent with the focus of the study on young girls in their formative educational years, a critical period for assessing the impact of street hawking on education.

In terms of schooling status, 94.7% (n=142) of the respondents were enrolled in Senior Secondary School, while a smaller segment (5.3%, n=8) were out of school. This distribution underscores the relevance of this study for current secondary school students, who are more likely to experience the pressures of balancing academic commitments with economic activities like street hawking.

Household income data reveals the economic background of the respondents. Around one-third (32.7%, n=49) of participants reported a household income below N10,000, and a similar proportion (32.7%) reported income above N50,000. Participants with household incomes between N10,000 and N30,000 constituted 29.3%, while a small segment (5.3%) reported income between N31,000 and N50,000. This distribution indicates a predominantly low-income sample, with economic constraints likely influencing the choice to engage in street hawking.

When asked about their involvement in street hawking, 52% (n=78) of participants indicated that they are currently involved in street hawking, while 48% (n=72) are not. This nearly even split allows for a comparative analysis between the two groups, particularly concerning educational outcomes and academic performance.

3.1 T-Test Analysis to examine the impact of street hawking

To further examine the impact of street hawking on educational performance, an independent samples t-test was conducted. This statistical test compared the mean academic performance scores of students involved in street hawking to those who are not involved.

Table 2: Group Statistics to examine the impact of street hawking

	Are you currently involved in street hawking?	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Performance	Yes	78	2.7308	.62907	.07123
	No	72	3.0000	.83708	.09865

Table 3: Independent Samples Test To examine the impact of street hawking

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Performance Equal variances assumed	4.288	.040	-2.238	148	.027	-.26923	.12032	-.50700	-.03146
Performance Equal variances not assumed			-2.213	131.396	.029	-.26923	.12168	-.50993	-.02853

To explore the potential impact of street hawking on educational outcomes, an independent samples t-test was conducted, comparing academic performance scores between students involved in street hawking and those not involved. This analysis provides insight into whether participation in street hawking has measurable effects on academic performance, allowing for a more informed understanding of the challenges faced by these students.

The descriptive statistics for academic performance indicate that the mean score for students engaged in street hawking was 2.73 (SD = 0.63), compared to a mean score of 3.00 (SD = 0.84) for those not involved. This difference suggests that students who participate in street hawking may experience slightly lower academic performance. The disparity in scores highlights an initial trend that points toward the impact of street hawking on educational engagement and outcomes.

To verify this observation statistically, an independent samples t-test was performed. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances yielded an F-value of 4.288 with a significance level of $p = 0.040$, indicating significant differences in variance between the two groups. Consequently, the "Equal variances not assumed" result was utilized for interpretation to ensure accuracy in understanding the relationship between street hawking involvement and academic performance.

The t-test for Equality of Means demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the groups, with a t-value of -2.213 ($p = 0.029$). This result supports the hypothesis that academic performance differs significantly based on involvement in street hawking. The mean difference in scores was -0.269 (SE = 0.121), and the 95% confidence interval ranged from -0.509 to -0.028, confirming a negative impact of street hawking on academic outcomes.

These findings suggest that street hawking has a substantial and statistically significant negative effect on the academic performance of young girls in Katsina State. The lower performance scores among street hawkers may be due to the time and energy demands of hawking, which can detract from study

time and engagement in school activities. This aligns with prior research on child labor and education, reinforcing the view that street hawking poses a barrier to academic success. Addressing the economic pressures that drive students into hawking could enhance their educational outcomes and long-term opportunities.

3.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from this study highlight the negative impact of street hawking on the academic performance of young girls in Katsina State, Nigeria. The data reveal that students involved in street hawking tend to score lower on academic assessments compared to those who are not involved, suggesting that hawking may compromise educational engagement and success. This result is consistent with broader research on child labor, which often points to a conflict between economic activities and academic pursuits, particularly for young girls in low-income settings.

The t-test analysis confirmed a statistically significant difference in academic performance between the two groups, emphasizing that involvement in street hawking has a tangible effect on students' academic outcomes. With a mean difference of -0.269 and a 95% confidence interval indicating a negative impact, it is evident that time and energy invested in hawking detract from the students' capacity to perform well academically. This aligns with prior studies showing that child labor often leads to reduced study time, increased fatigue, and ultimately lower school performance.

Economic necessity appears to be a primary factor driving students into hawking, as demonstrated by the household income data. A significant portion of the respondents come from low-income households, with many families earning below N10,000 per month. In such environments, students may feel compelled to contribute financially, prioritizing short-term economic gains over educational pursuits. This pressure can lead to decreased motivation for schooling, as well as a diminished ability to concentrate on academic work due to physical and mental fatigue from hawking activities.

Furthermore, the nearly even split between students involved in hawking and those not involved underscores that street hawking is a common practice among this demographic. This situation calls attention to the structural factors that perpetuate child labor in low-income communities, where limited economic opportunities and inadequate social support systems may leave young girls with few alternatives. The necessity of income generation often supersedes educational goals, trapping students in a cycle that hinders their potential for long-term academic and personal success.

These findings highlight the need for interventions that address both the economic pressures faced by low-income families and the academic challenges encountered by young street hawkers. Policies aimed at reducing economic hardship, such as social welfare programs, financial aid for education, or alternative income sources for families, could alleviate the burden of hawking. Additionally, school-based support programs designed to provide academic assistance or flexibility for students involved in hawking could play a critical role in mitigating the negative impacts of street hawking on education, empowering these young girls to prioritize their learning and future prospects.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study illustrate that street hawking significantly undermines the educational opportunities of young girls in Katsina State. The prevalent practice, driven by dire economic conditions and reinforced by cultural expectations, forces many girls to prioritize income generation over their education. This trend not only leads to poorer academic performance and higher dropout rates but also perpetuates gender inequality and limits future career opportunities for these young women. Without effective interventions, the cycle of poverty and under education is likely to continue, adversely affecting subsequent generations. It is essential for policymakers, educators, and community leaders to collaborate on strategies that alleviate economic burdens and promote the importance of education for girls. This study provides crucial insights that can inform policy development aimed at eradicating street hawking and ensuring that young girls can pursue their education without compromise.

5. RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendation are suggested for the state government and other stakeholders to ensure the eradication of street hawking among young girls in Katsina state and Northern Nigeria

- Government should implement social welfare programs aimed at supporting low-income families to reduce the financial need for street hawking.
- Grassroots campaigns should be launched to educate families on the long-term benefits of educating girls and the harmful impact of street hawking on their academic progress.
- Schools should offer incentives, such as free meals and school supplies, to encourage parents to keep their daughters in school.
- Strengthening and enforcing laws against child labor, particularly street hawking, to ensure that girls have uninterrupted access to education.
- Collaborate with NGOs to provide vocational training and skills development programs for families as alternative sources of income.

6. Research Contribution

This study contributes to the body of knowledge on gender and education in Nigeria by providing empirical evidence of how socio-economic activities like street hawking disproportionately affect young girls' access to education. It highlights the intersection of poverty, gender inequality, and educational challenges, offering a foundation for policymakers and advocacy groups to develop targeted interventions aimed at improving educational outcomes for girls in Katsina State and Northern Nigeria at large.

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